

NUTRITION AND INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH CYSTIC FIBROSIS

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Annotation. Hereditary pathology is relevant not only from the medical point of view, it is a problem that has its socio-economic significance for the family. According to various sources, the main molecular-genetic aspects of cystic fibrosis in different forms of genotypes have been studied up to now, diagnostic algorithms of examination, treatment and dispensary observation of patients have been developed. The aim of our study was to investigate the severity of nutritional disorders and indicators of physical development in young children with cystic fibrosis. We studied 30 children aged from birth to 3 years. Nutritional deficiency of different severity at admission to hospital was revealed in 60% of children with cystic fibrosis, the lowest anthropometric indices were found in children with cystic fibrosis in the first year of life.

Key words: children, early age, nutritional disorders, cystic fibrosis.

Аннотация. Наследственная патология является актуальной не только с медицинской точки зрения, это проблема, которая имеет свою социально-экономическую значимость для семьи. Согласно данным различных источников, до сегодняшнего дня изучены главные молекулярно-генетические аспекты Муковисцидоза при различных формах генотипов, разработаны диагностические алгоритмы обследования, лечения и диспансерного наблюдения больных. Целью нашего исследования было изучить степень тяжести нарушения питания и показатели физического развития у детей раннего возраста при Муковисцидозе. Нами было исследовано 30 детей в возрасте от рождения до 3-х лет. Недостаточность питания различной степени тяжести при поступлении в стационар выявлена у 60% детей с муковисцидозом, наиболее низкие антропометрические показатели отмечаются у детей с муковисцидозом на первом году жизни.

Ключевые слова: дети, ранний возраст, нарушения питания, муковисцидоз.

Annotatsiya. Irsiy patologiya nafaqat tibbiy nuqtai nazardan, balki oila uchun o'ziga xos ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan muammodir. Turli manbalarga ko'ra, hozirgi kunga qadar genotiplarning turli shakllarida mukovistsidozning asosiy molekulyar genetik jihatlari o'rganilib, bemorlarni tekshirish, davolash va kuzatish uchun diagnostika algoritmlari ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqotimizning maqsadi mukovitsidoz bilan kasallangan bolalarda ovqatlanishning buzilishi og'irligini va jismoniy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlarini o'rganish edi. Tug'ilgandan 3 yoshgacha bo'lgan 30 nafar bolani o'rgandik. Kasalxonaga yotqizilgandan so'ng turli darajadagi ovqatlanish buzilishlari mukovitsidozli bolalarning 60 foizida aniqlandi, eng past antropometrik ko'rsatkichlar hayotning birinchi yilidagi bolalarda kuzatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: bolalar, erta yosh, ovqatlanishning buzilishi, mukovitsidoz.

Relevance. Cystic fibrosis (CF) remains one of the most complex hereditary chronic multisystem diseases in both adults and children. Hereditary pathologies represent an important problem, not only in medicine, but also has its own socio-economic significance for the family. According to various sources, the main molecular genetic aspects of Cystic Fibrosis in various forms and genotypes have been studied to date, and diagnostic algorithms for examination, treatment and follow-up of patients have been developed. In pediatric practice, CF is often disguised as various diseases of the respiratory system, liver and pancreas, pathology of the ENT

organs, acute infectious diseases, etc. [1]. Early neonatal screening, which began to be used in 2020 in Uzbekistan, made it possible to diagnose CF in a timely manner and even before the appearance of clinical symptoms (ideally at the age of 1 month), as well as to prescribe complex basic therapy in a timely manner. In many patients, cystic fibrosis is severe and requires constant complex drug treatment, kinesitherapy, individual selection of enzyme replacement therapy, diet and therapeutic nutrition. From birth, CF patients are predisposed to developing bacterial respiratory tract infections. Numerous studies have shown that poor nutritional status in patients with CF is an independent factor in worsening lung function, life expectancy, and increased mortality. Chronic bronchopulmonary infection in most cases develops in the first months or years of life of a child with CF, and yet, problems regarding this severe multi-organ disease remain unresolved. This is predetermined by a biological mechanism associated with a genetically determined defect in the synthesis of CFTR. In the bronchopulmonary system, a defect in CFTR synthesis leads to high viscosity of bronchial secretions and decreased mucociliary clearance [3]. Currently, an important goal in the treatment of cystic fibrosis is to slow the progression of bronchopulmonary disorders, since deterioration of lung function primarily leads to a decrease in the quality and life expectancy of these patients [2].

Diet therapy and enzyme replacement therapy form an important part of complex therapy for cystic fibrosis. A significant stage in treatment was the use of a high-calorie diet since 1988 without limiting the consumption of fats, which were previously almost completely excluded from the diet. Nutritional status (NS) is understood as the result of the influence of the nature of nutrition and nutritional factors, manifested in the objective parameters of the body, its biological media and components. In a child with cystic fibrosis, NS reflects the severity of the patient's condition and is a criterion for control over the course of the disease. Malnutrition often accompanies cystic fibrosis and can be both a symptom and a concomitant pathology [4,5,6].

Numerous studies have shown that poor nutritional status in patients with CF is an independent factor in worsening lung function, life expectancy, and increased mortality. Low nutritional status in cystic fibrosis is due to increased energy requirements with reduced intake and high losses of nutrients and energy due to malabsorption [5]. This, along with improved anthropometric indicators, contributed to an increase in life expectancy. A special dietary approach (increasing the energy value, amount of protein and fat in the diet) is still used today [1]. However, the wide range of recommended energy requirements (from 110 to 200% of the physiological norm), which applies to the general population of patients with cystic fibrosis, is a limiting factor for choosing a diet adequate in terms of energy value for each patient. The criteria for selecting individual energy needs remain not fully studied. Factors of individual metabolic risk, the degree of nutritional deficiency, the state of actual nutrition, the balance of macronutrients, the patient's eating behavior, the period and severity of the disease are not taken into account. Low nutritional status in cystic fibrosis is due to increased energy requirements with reduced intake and high losses of nutrients and energy due to malabsorption. Therefore, the organization of therapeutic nutrition, an integral part of the complex therapy of patients with CF, is an urgent problem in pediatric pulmonology and nutrition [6]. The significant volume and high cost of life-saving medications and measures make timely and comprehensive treatment of CF patients difficult.

The purpose of the study was to study the severity of malnutrition and indicators of physical development in young children with cystic fibrosis.

Materials and research methods. We conducted a study of 30 children with CF aged 1 year to 3 years, of which the age category were children; 8 patients (26.6%) 1 year of life, 12

patients (46.8%) 2 years of age and 8 (26.6%) patients 3 years of age. All children underwent the necessary medical examination provided for by the Standards for the provision of medical care to children with MB according to the clinical protocol. In addition, a comprehensive assessment of nutritional status was carried out, based on anamnestic, clinical, anthropometric, laboratory and functional data. To assess NS, in addition to clinical and biochemical methods, anthropometric (somatometric) data are traditionally used - body weight, height, body mass index (BMI), which in children are calculated in accordance with age and gender. To process anthropometric data, the WHO Who-Anthro program, version 1.0.4 (for children under 5 years of age) was used to calculate Z-scores for height/age (HAZ), BMI/age (BAZ), and weight/age (WAZ) . The severity of malnutrition was determined based on the WHO malnutrition classifications (Waterlow J.C., 1992), ICD 10 (E40-46).

Results. All patients were diagnosed with a mixed (pulmonary-intestinal) form of CF. When assessing the severity of CF, it was assessed using the Shwachman-Brasfield scale, which revealed that 10 (33.3%) patients had severe CF, 18 (60.0%) had moderate CF, and 2 (6.7%) patients had mild CF. The main complaints during hospitalization were: loss of appetite (78.2%) and loss of body weight (70.6%). More than half of the patients had weakness, lethargy, fatigue (63.5%), dry, unproductive cough (57.3%), abdominal pain occurred in 44% of children. Severe chronic exocrine pancreatic insufficiency was detected in the majority of patients - 27 (90%), 3 (10%) were diagnosed with moderate pancreatic insufficiency, 7 (3%).

The patients were divided according to malnutrition (protein energy deficiency) into three groups: 1 gr - 13 (43.3%) children with malnutrition -2CO, second - 10 (33.3%) children with malnutrition -3CO, third - 7 (23.3%) of patients without nutritional disorders(fig.1). In all children with cystic fibrosis, anthropometric indicators were assessed (weight and length (height) of the body, skin-fat folds were measured using caliperometry, as well as shoulder circumference. For all parameters, the Z-score in children with CF was observed according to standard deviations in physical development -63, 6%). % of children had an average degree of body weight deficiency $HAZ < -2SD$.

30 children with CF aged 0 to 3

Figure1. Groups of patients according to the degree of malnutrition

The level of insulin-like growth factor-1 in children of group 1 (27.2%) was <23.45 (normal <60.0) ng/ml) in children of group 2 < 28.2 ng/ml, and in 3 g without malnutrition <133.0 ng/ml(fig.2). Growth failure is an important problem in children with CF.

The main levels of IGF-1 in groups

Figure2. The main levels of IGF-1 in groups

When assessing the physical development of patients with cystic fibrosis depending on their age, it was found that the lowest anthropometric indicators were detected in the first year of life; it was established that 18 (60%) patients with cystic fibrosis, mainly in the first year and upon admission to the hospital, had acute or chronic malnutrition varying degrees of severity, which required special attention when organizing therapeutic nutrition in a hospital.

Conclusions. Studies of the protein-energy status of children with cystic fibrosis, which included indicators reflecting the main aspects of nutritional status: subjective data on nutritional status, anthropometric indicators, visceral protein parameters, assessment of fat reserves, the presence of immunodeficiency. A comprehensive study of the degree of trophic disorders and adequate nutritional correction will significantly improve the quality of life of patients and the prognosis of the disease. In patients with cystic fibrosis and malnutrition, regardless of the degree of severity determined by anthropometric indices, biochemical parameters characterizing protein metabolism are within the reference values, which may be a consequence of chronic bronchopulmonary inflammation.

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